

Strategic Agility in Technology-Driven Business Environments: A Review of Adaptive Strategies Employed by Small Businesses

Justice Ngonidzashe Muchineripi

*Department of Management, Faculty of Management and Public Administration Sciences
Walter Sisulu University, Butterworth Campus N2, Ibika Industrial Area, Butterworth, South Africa*

Technological developments fueled by the Fourth Industrial Revolution have resulted in disruptions and changes which require businesses to be responsive and adaptive. In the wake of this reality, strategic agility offers an opportunity for small businesses to adapt to changes and seize opportunities emerging in the business environment, as well as minimise the impact of threats. This paper examines adaptive strategies employed by small businesses to build and sustain strategic agility. Through a literature review, research established that lean innovation, digital transformation, strategic partnerships and agile workforce development are key strategies used for cultivating strategic agility in an organisation. The dynamic capability theory was used as an underpinning theory to explore the development of adaptive strategies that enhance strategic agility in small businesses. The research also provides conclusions and implications. Moreover, the research identified gaps that should be addressed by future research.

Keywords: Strategic agility, technology, adaptive strategy, dynamic capabilities, fourth industrial revolution

In the contemporary era, characterised by globalisation and rapid technological advancements, the business environment has increasingly become complex and dynamic. Changes in the global economy, compounded by technological and overall market dynamics, significantly impact the business of all sizes, especially small businesses (Ghobakhloo et al., 2022). Technologies such as artificial intelligence, cloud computing, data analytics and virtual reality have been driving market changes that disrupt traditional businesses. Small businesses, also referred to as SMMEs in the South African context, are expected to leverage technology to achieve their short- and long-term goals. These goals may include, but are not limited to, performance, market share, innovations, business growth and competitiveness in the market. Whilst technology has the potential to enhance attainment of goals and outcomes mentioned above, Hendrawan et al. (2024) note that efforts to leverage technology among small businesses are impeded by an array of challenges, such as inadequate management skills, lack of access to business capital in the form of loans and grants, as well as access to technological infrastructure. All these challenges

impede effective implementation of business functions such as human resource management, marketing, innovation and management in general (Malki, 2023). Furthermore, challenges such as stiff competition from both local and international players also affect small businesses' capacity to maintain their existing market share and attract new customers. This has been worsened by the fact that, more than ever before, the business environment has become more dynamic, and businesses of all sizes, including small businesses, ought to be able to respond in a flexible and effective manner so that they can adapt and exploit opportunities that may emerge as a result of the changes. To that end, Ghobakhloo et al. (2022) recommend that, as the most vulnerable in the business environment, small businesses should not only be able to anticipate changes but should deploy strategic abilities to survive the changes and thrive in the prevailing environment.

According to Tarba et al. (2023), strategic agility is defined as a business's ability to effectively and swiftly change its operations, strategies, resources and structures to adapt to the new conditions in the macro environment. Invoking strategic abilities includes quickly adapting to unexpected challenges and being decisive, thus enabling the business to offset the impact of negative changes and to exploit new opportunities that might arise because of such changes. It is important for small businesses to have higher levels of strategic agility because it facilitates the development of sustainable competitive advantage, enhances financial planning, strategic management and optimises resource allocation. Advocates for strategic agility in small businesses also argue that it provides a comprehensive approach to entrepreneurial decision-making by putting them in a better position to make better decisions based on current data (Abrokwah-Larbi, 2024). This also demonstrates the importance of data in building strategic agility and technology applications, such as machine learning, which has improved data analytics, thereby enhancing data-based decision-making. Whilst larger enterprises normally invest in research and development

Author Note

Justice Ngonidzashe Muchineripi, Department of Management
Faculty of Management and Public Administration Sciences
Walter Sisulu University, Butterworth Campus N2, Ibika Industrial
Area, Butterworth, South Africa
E-mail: jmuchineripi@wsu.ac.za
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8058-731X>
I have no known conflict of interest to disclose.
Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to
Justice Ngonidzashe Muchineripi, Department of Management
Faculty of Management and Public Administration Sciences
Walter Sisulu University, Butterworth Campus N2, Ibika Industrial
Area, Butterworth, South Africa
E-mail: jmuchineripi@wsu.ac.za

departments as well as digital transformation, small businesses should adopt a creative and agile approach (Kawung et al., 2022). Due to their size, small businesses can be flexible enough to adjust to changes in the business environment; however, they also face challenges which negatively impact their capacity to respond and adapt.

This paper reviews extant literature on how small businesses build strategic agility in the ever-dynamic, technology-driven environments largely fuelled by the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR). The paper focuses on four adaptive strategies, namely digital transformation, lean innovation, agile workforce development and strategic partnerships. These strategies are analysed and assessed in light of the dynamic capabilities theory, which puts emphasis on building, reconfiguring and integrating available resources to address changes in the business environment. In particular, the paper seeks to address the following research question: What strategies do small businesses use to attain strategic agility in technology-driven business environments? The review explores literature from studies conducted in various contexts, such as emerging developed economies, technology-intensive industries and those that need technology just as a supporting tool, to draw insights that inform how small businesses leverage technology to build and deploy strategic agilities.

Strategic Agility

Strategic agility is an important capability in business organisations because, together with other factors, it determines the extent to which a business is able to rapidly and flexibly respond to changes in the business environment. Strategic agility is defined by Al-Taweel and Al-Hawary (2021) as the ability to identify and respond to changes in the business environment. These changes may occur in both the internal and external environment. From a construct perspective, Sampath and Krishnamoorthy (2017) describe strategic agility as a complex construct that includes anticipating, recognising and sensing market opportunities emanating from evolving conditions as well as implementing innovative solutions to help the business adapt. Drawing on the definitions provided above, it can be inferred that environmental changes (threats & opportunities), business environment and the speed at which a business can identify and respond to changes are key themes that can be identified. Accordingly, this study defines strategic agility as the small businesses' ability to detect changes in dynamic, fast-paced environments and to promptly respond by seizing market opportunities and maintaining competitiveness through building, combining, enhancing, mobilising, and reconfiguring their capabilities, thereby achieving and sustaining superior performance beyond their competitors.

Theoretical Framework

Dynamic Capabilities Theory

The study was informed by the Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT). The theory advances that a firm's competitive advantage comes from its ability to reconfigure its external and internal competencies. This is done in order to navigate the ever-changing business environments by aligning, altering and expanding a firm's resource base to flexibly respond to the dynamic business trends (Kapoor & Aggarwal, 2020). The DCT underscores the importance of dynamic capabilities for businesses of all sizes, including small businesses.

Dynamic capabilities refer to a business or firm's capacity to reconfigure, build and integrate external and internal competences/resources to shape and address changes in the business environment (Teece et al., 1997). According to Teece (2007), dynamic capabilities are based on various change routines, such as new product development and environmental analysis, which then inform investment choices. Dynamic capabilities are developed through the implementation of effective entrepreneurial and creative managerial acts, such as pioneers' new markets, products and processes (Hussler et al., 2012). Dynamic capabilities relate to the development of strategic agility in business because strategic capabilities enable businesses to be agile by improving the extent to which they effectively respond to market changes. Furthermore, Cavusgil, Seggie, and Talay (2007) state that dynamic capabilities are a reflection of the degree and speed with which business enterprises' competences and distinctive resources are realigned or aligned to address threats and match opportunities. Dynamic capabilities manifest through 3 dimensions, which are sensing changes in the business environment, reconfiguring resources and seizing abilities, which are crucial for a firm's adaptation process. Through sensing capabilities, a firm is able to identify threats and opportunities in the business environment and interpret new information that may emerge as a result of the changes (Teece, 2007). Dynamic capability also increases the potential of the business to identify relevant data and information that can be utilised to make informed decisions on the direction the business is supposed to take (Gremme & Wohlgemuth, 2017). Businesses that are deemed to have dynamic capabilities are regarded as being quick in adjusting to any changes that take place within the business environment they are operating under (Teece, 2007). Quick response within a business allows the business to grow exponentially, as it can easily dictate strengths and weaknesses within the business environment. South African businesses can benefit by adopting dynamic capability principles to reduce their failure rate, as it can increase their competitiveness. With the current study examining strategies that can be used to develop strategic agility by businesses, the dynamic capability theory thus informs the study.

Method

The researcher adopted a narrative research review methodology in order to examine strategies that can be utilised when developing strategic agility by small businesses. In a narrative literature review approach, the researcher has to synthesise literature which is already in existence to allow subjective selection of the relevant literature that is in line with the subject matter under study (Djafar et al., 2021). Data was gathered from sources such as these, periodical publications and relevant reports. In addition, information was also collected from scientific databases that include Research Gate, Science Direct, Wiley Online, Sage, and Google Scholar. Only articles on strategic agility published between 2015 and 2025 were considered for this study. The narrative analysis approach was used. After following the process of gathering literature, the researcher familiarised themselves with the relevant data and themes that were extracted from the literature.

Discussion

Adaptive Strategies for Achieving Strategic Agility

Adaptive strategies that can be utilised by small businesses in

building stronger strategic agility will be discussed under this section. These strategies are lean innovation, digital transformation, strategic partnerships and agile workforce development.

Lean Innovation

A notable strategy that can be leveraged by small businesses to build strategic agility in technology-driven environments is lean innovation. Lean innovation refers to an innovation process that involves the adoption of quicker, iterative learning cycles and the eradication of wastage whilst ensuring that customers' preferences remain the main focus of the whole process (Corvello, Straffalaci, & Filice, 2022). Lean innovation is important in enhancing strategic agility among small businesses because it enables resource-constrained small businesses to effectively respond to changes in the business environment. This is confirmed in a study conducted by Adomoko et al. (2022) who established that small businesses that follow the lean innovation practices and processes, such as the minimum viable product, have a higher likelihood of successfully adapting to changes in the macro environment.

The implementation of lean innovation in small businesses is considered to be successful by measuring market demand and the introduction of cost-effective prototypes, which allows quicker pivots that are informed by the feedback of customers. Lean innovation is a key strategy in building strategic agility for small businesses; however, it is more effective when it is implemented in businesses operating in the technology sector (Omowole et al., 2024). A study by Mofolasayo et al. (2022) recognised that when innovative strategies are placed on iterative development, they can influence the competitive advantage of a business positively. In a study by Kerexiev (2024) the importance of lean innovation was reiterated, showing that by prioritising flexibility and speed, small businesses can equip themselves to compete with established businesses in the market. Building strategic agility through lean innovation is considered a strategic business action that can lead to various benefits that can be enjoyed by small businesses. However, a stronger innovation culture is required to effectively implement lean innovations, which is challenging for risk-averse entrepreneurs (Deakins & Bensemann, 2019).

Digital Transformation

Vandana et al. (2024) describe digital transformation as a process utilised by businesses to integrate digital technologies in their operations to enhance the effectiveness of the business. These may include, among others, customer experience, creating new business models, and streamlining operations and decision-making. Digital technologies are renowned for their transformative effect on society and other aspects of life, particularly in business. Supporting this assertion, Akman et al. (2023) forward that the adoption and integration of digital technologies in businesses seems to have transformative effects on their operations. Business operations are meant to enhance customer engagement, scalability and efficiency, which are all determinants of strategic agility that can benefit from the implementation of digital transformation in businesses (Zhang, Fong, & Yamoah Agyemang, 2021). Accordingly, digital transformation is an important factor that enables small businesses to develop and build the ability to identify changes in the business environment, scan for threats and opportunities, as well as respond to those changes before competitors. This is important because it enables small businesses to survive in technology-driven markets.

The relationship between agility and digital technology has drawn keen interest from various researchers. Rahmi and Mursyidin (2024) in their study discovered that there is a positive correlation between adaptability and agility. The major finding of this study was on how the integration of artificial intelligence has led to the evolution of hotel booking platforms. In another study conducted by Faruque et al. (2024) it was stated that small businesses were kept afloat by digital technology during the lockdown, as there was an increase in demand for contactless services due to COVID-19. Current demand and preferences by consumers are shifting to the use of digital tools and technology, as it offers convenience. There has been an increase in the use of digital tools such as social media, e-commerce websites and data analytics, which are enhancing the experience of consumers when interacting with various businesses (Akman et al., 2023). Akman et al. (2024) further stated that these digital platforms have been a game-changer within the business environment through predicting the future, looking for opportunities and threats that improve the decision-making of any business. Adding to this conversation, Hokmabadi et al. (2024) alludes that digital technologies have a vital role to play in small businesses to ensure that their decision-making processes are influenced by data-driven decisions to optimise their business operations. Based on this discussion, it can be concluded that for businesses to develop and build strategic agility, digital transformation plays a pivotal role.

Strategic Partnerships

Forming strategic alliances and partnerships is also considered an effective strategy for improving strategic agility among small businesses. A strategic partnership is defined as a formal agreement between two or more enterprises to work towards attaining mutually beneficial goals. Strategic enables businesses to capitalise and leverage the strengths of each involved partners to respond to changes in the business environment and offset the impact of competitive pressures (Pfaff, 2023). Getting into partnerships enables businesses to thrive, innovate, and maintain a competitive edge by sharing knowledge and expertise. Furthermore, strategic partnerships allow small businesses to access resources, expertise, and markets they lack internally (Tsilionis & Wautelet, 2022). These collaborations enhance agility by enabling resource sharing and risk mitigation. Christofi (2024) conducted an empirical investigation of multinational corporations and found that strategic partnerships, particularly with technology providers, were critical for fostering agility.

Small businesses are often confronted by a lack of resources; hence, getting into a partnership with other businesses can enable them to survive in the technology-driven business environment (Quansah & Hartz, 2021). Possible partnerships for small businesses include universities and technology firms, which can provide them with knowledge and technology that enable small businesses to adapt to market changes. Adomako et al. (2022) established that small businesses formed alliances with international partners to circumvent regulatory challenges, enabling them to access modern technologies, thus enhancing their strategic agility. While partnerships are an important element for building strategic agility, it should be noted that managing partnerships requires alignment of goals and trust, which can be challenging for resource-constrained firms

Agile Workforce Development

An agile workforce refers to a flexible and adaptable workforce that

can quickly respond to new business needs and market dynamics (Quansah, Hartz, & Salipante, 2022). Developing an agile workforce involves fostering a culture of collaboration, talent sharing, and continuous learning, with a focus on skills development and proactive workforce planning (Marcazzan, Campagnolo, & Gianecchini, 2022). This enables small businesses to maintain their competitiveness in the ever-dynamic business environment powered by continued technological advancements. Reinhold (2024) warns that small businesses need to invest in human resource development to build a workforce that is equipped to respond to changes in the business environment, particularly the market. Essentially, small business needs to build an agile workforce that values continuous learning and upskilling to enhance their flexibility and adaptability to respond to technology-driven market changes (Elanthi & Dhanabhakym, 2021).

The significant role that is played by human resources in building strategic agility is encapsulated in existing literature. Storme et al. (2020) describe how an agile workforce is built by stating that firms need to effectively implement cross-functional teams and talent management. In the prevailing Fourth Industrial Revolution era, small businesses ought to train and upskill their workforce so that they can leverage digital tools such as data analytics, e-commerce, social media, artificial intelligence and cloud computing to position their firms for adaptability. The prominent role of an agile workforce is demonstrated in mixed methods research conducted on 343 Spanish businesses in the service industry, which established that workforce agility supported business performance and resilience in uncertain environments (García et al., 2024). Strategies for promoting and building workforce agility among small businesses also include encouraging a culture of experimentation and adopting a flat organisational structure. This is more typical in tech startups, which use cross-functional teams to promote quick decision-making and innovation (Ajgaonkar, Neelam, & Wiemann, 2022). However, limited budgets for training and resistance to change among employees can impede workforce agility.

Conclusion and Implications of the Study

The review highlighted the importance of strategic agility in promoting small business adaptability in the dynamic, technology-driven business environments. The research also demonstrates strategic agility's role in ensuring that small businesses remain relevant and competitive even in the midst of an unstable business environment, which is largely driven by continuous technological advancements. The paper established that through lean innovation, digital transformation, strategic partnerships, and agile workforce development, small businesses can navigate the challenges of rapid technological change and resource constraints. Available literature underscores the effectiveness of these strategies in enhancing competitiveness and performance. However, barriers such as resource limitations and resistance to change require careful management. Small business leaders must prioritise sensing mechanisms, scalable technologies, collaborative networks, and workforce agility to achieve strategic agility. Drawing on the findings above, it is imperative for practitioners such as business managers and owners to emphasise building strategic agility necessary for adapting to technology-driven changes in the business environment. Furthermore, there is a need for specific policy interventions to position small businesses to develop strategic agility by providing them with necessary skills, funding, promoting

partnerships and innovations.

Recommendations and Further Research

The current study relied on secondary data to address research questions; thus, future research should investigate the relationship between determinants of strategic agility and strategic agility in small businesses operating in the South African environment. Conducting such research will provide insights into the context-specific nature of the relationship between adaptive strategies and small businesses' strategic agility. Furthermore, future research should also explore the role of strategic agility in fostering small business performance in the 4IR era. The 4IR is characterised by hyper-changes, which normally affect small businesses in a negative way. Also, future research should explore entrepreneurs' perceptions of the importance of building strategic agility for business, so that insights into what entrepreneurs think can be established. This will help identify gaps that can be addressed by targeted and context-specific interventions. Moreover, research should focus on developing practical, context-specific frameworks for small businesses to assess their agility and identify areas for improvement. Additionally, the role of government support and policy in fostering strategic agility among small businesses in a digital economy is an important area for further investigation.

References

- Abrokwah-Larbi, K. (2024). Transforming metaverse marketing into strategic agility in SMEs through mediating roles of IMT and CI: Theoretical framework and research propositions. *Journal of Contemporary Marketing Science*, 7(1), 56-83.
- Adomako, S., Amankwah-Amoah, J., Donbesuur, F., Ahsan, M., Danso, A., & Uddin, M. (2022). Strategic agility of SMEs in emerging economies: Antecedents, consequences and boundary conditions. *International Business Review*, 31(6), 102032.
- Ajgaonkar, S., Neelam, N.G., & Wiemann, J. (2022). Drivers of workforce agility: A dynamic capability perspective. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 30(4), 951-982.
- Al Malki, M. (2023). A review of sustainable growth challenges faced by small and medium enterprises. *International Journal for Global Academic and Scientific Research*, 2(1), 53-67.
- AlTaweel, I.R., & Al-Hawary, S.I. (2021). The mediating role of innovation capability on the relationship between strategic agility and organizational performance. *Sustainability*, 13(14), 7564.
- Cavusgil, E., Seggie, S.H., & Talay, M.B. (2007). Dynamic capabilities view: Foundations and research agenda. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 15(2), 159-166.
- Christofi, K., Chourides, P., & Papageorgiou, G. (2024). Cultivating strategic agility An empirical investigation into best practice. *Global Business and Organizational Excellence*, 43(3), 89-105.
- Corvello, V., Straffalaci, V., & Filice, L. (2022). Small business antifragility: How research and innovation can help survive crises and thrive. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation Management*, 26(3/4), 252-268.
- Deakins, D., & Bensemann, J.O. (2019). Achieving innovation in a lean environment: How innovative small firms overcome resource constraints. *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 23(4), 1950037.
- Djafar, H., Yunus, R., Pomalato, S. W. D., & Rasid, R. (2021). Qualitative and quantitative paradigm constellation in educational research methodology. *International Journal of Educational Research and Social Sciences*, 2(2), 339-345.
- Elanthi, M.B., & Dhanabhakym, M. (2021). Agile workforce: A post-pandemic revival plan for SMEs. In M.B. Elanthi and M. Dhanabhakym (Eds.), *Handbook of research on sustaining SMEs and entrepreneurial innovation in the Post-COVID-19 Era* (pp. 1-18). IGI Global Scientific Publishing.
- Faruque, M.O., Chowdhury, S., Rabbani, G., & Nure, A. (2024). Technology adoption and digital transformation in small businesses: Trends, challenges, and opportunities. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 6(10), 36948.
- Ghobakhloo, M., Iranmanesh, M., Vilkas, M., Grybauskas, A., & Amran, A. (2022). Drivers and barriers of Industry 4.0 technology adoption among manufacturing SMEs: A systematic review and transformation roadmap. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 33(6), 1029-1058.

- Gremme, K.M., & Wohlgemuth, V. (2017). Dynamic capabilities: A systematic literature review of theory and practice. *European Journal of Management Issues*, 25(1), 30-35.
- Hendrawan, S.A., Chatra, A., Iman, N., Hidayatullah, S., & Suprayitno, D. (2024). Digital transformation in MSMEs: Challenges and opportunities in technology management. *Jurnal Informasi dan Teknologi*, 6(2), 141-149.
- Hokmabadi, H., Rezvani, S.M., & de Matos, C.A. (2024). Business resilience for small and medium enterprises and startups by digital transformation and the role of marketing capabilities: A systematic review. *Systems*, 12(6), 220.
- Hussler, C., Pénin, J., Dietrich, M., Burger-Helmchen, T., & Kuuluvainen, A. (2012). How to concretize dynamic capabilities? Theory and examples. *Journal of Strategy and Management*, 5(4), 381-392.
- Jooss, S., Collings, D.G., McMackin, J., & Dickmann, M. (2024). A skills-matching perspective on talent management: Developing strategic agility. *Human Resource Management*, 63(1), 141-157.
- Kapoor, M., & Aggarwal, V. (2020). Tracing the economics behind dynamic capabilities theory. *International Journal of Innovation Science*, 12(2), 187-201.
- Kawung, G.M., Mintardjo, C.M., Rompas, W.F., & Rogi, M.H. (2022). Digital technology transformation of SMEs: Indonesian case study. *American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation*, 1(6), 56-60.
- Kereziev, I. (2024). Advantages of the Lean Approach for initiating and developing a small business in a VUCA environment. *Vanguard Scientific Instruments in Management*, 20(1), 215-222.
- Mancuso, I., Petruzzelli, A.M., Panniello, U., & Vaia, G. (2025). Business model innovation in the banking sector: How digital technologies transform innovation drivers in value mechanisms innovations. *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*, 75, 101858.
- Marcazzan, E., Campagnolo, D., & Gianecchini, M. (2022). Reaction or anticipation? Resilience in small- and medium-sized enterprises. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 29(5), 764-788.
- Mofolasayo, A., Young, S., Martinez, P., & Ahmad, R. (2022). How to adapt lean practices in SMEs to support Industry 4.0 in manufacturing. *Procedia Computer Science*, 200, 934-943.
- Omowole, B.M., Olufemi-Philips, A.Q., Ofadile, O.C., Eyo-Udo, N.L., & Ewim, S.E. (2024). Conceptualizing agile business practices for enhancing SME resilience to economic shocks. *International Journal of Scholarly Research and Reviews*, 5(2), 070-088.
- Pfaff, Y.M. (2023). Agility and digitalization: why strategic agility is a success factor for mastering digitalization-evidence from Industry 4.0 implementations across a supply chain. *International Journal of Physical Distribution and Logistics Management*, 53(5/6), 660-684.
- Quansah, E., & Hartz, D.E. (2021). Strategic adaptation: Leadership lessons for small business survival and success. *American Journal of Business*, 36(3/4), 190-207.
- Quansah, E., Hartz, D.E., & Salipante, P. (2022). Adaptive practices in SMEs: Leveraging dynamic capabilities for strategic adaptation. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 29(7), 1130-1148.
- Rahmi, R., & Mursyidin, M. (2024). Independence and adaptability: Building resilience and competitiveness for small and medium-sized enterprises in the digital era. *Golden Ratio of Marketing and Applied Psychology of Business*, 4(1), 22-44.
- Reinhold, K. (2024). Building resilience: Pillars of workforce agility at organizational and individual levels in SMEs. In K. Reinhold (Ed.), *Small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) resilience: Strategies for risk and crisis management* (pp. 231-247). Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham.
- Tarba, S.Y., Frynas, J.G., Liu, Y., Wood, G., Sarala, R.M., & Fainshmidt, S. (2023). Strategic agility in international business. *Journal of World Business*, 58(2), 101411.
- Teece, D.J. (2007). Explicating dynamic capabilities: The nature and microfoundations of (sustainable) enterprise performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 28(13), 1319-1350.
- Tsilionis, K., & Wautetlet, Y. (2022). A model-driven framework to support strategic agility: Value-added perspective. *Information and Software Technology*, 141, 106734.
- Vandana, Sangwa, N.R., Ertz, M., & Shashi (2024). Sustainable and resilient cold chains: Enhancing adaptability, consistency, and digital transformation for success in a turbulent market. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 33(7), 6689-6715.
- Zhang, Y., Fong, P.S.W., & Yamoah Agyemang, D. (2021). What should be focused on when digital transformation hits industries? Literature review of business management adaptability. *Sustainability*, 13(23), 13447.

Received October 1, 2025

Revision received November 27, 2025

Accepted November 30, 2025